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Review Article

Development and Assessment of Naturally Derived Tamarind Kernel Powder as Disintegrant in Beta-Blocker Atenolol Tablet

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ABSTRACT

One common cardiovascular condition that needs to be effectively managed is hypertension. A beta-blocker called atenolol is frequently used to treat hypertension. Using tamarind seed kernel powder (TSKP) as a natural disintegrant, the study sought to create and assess atenolol tablets. TSKP was used in the formulation of the tablets, and their physical properties, dissolves profile, and disintegration time were assessed. The tablets quick and total dissolving, as demonstrated by the results, suggested that TSKP might be used as a natural disintegrant. By demonstrating the feasibility of using Tamarind seed kernel powder is a naturally occurring disintegrant in atenolol tablets, this work offers a feasible approach for the creation of naturally derived excipient-based hypertension therapy drugs.

INTRODUCTION

Millions of people throughout the world suffer from hypertension, a common cardiovascular condition that requires efficient treatment methods. A typical beta-blocker used to treat hypertension is atenolol, which lowers heart rate and blood pressure¹. For atenolol, tablet formulation is a commonly utilized dosage form because of its patient compliance and ease of administration. However, synthetic disintegrants, which are typically used in regular tablets, have drawbacks, including the propensity to irritate the

gastrointestinal tract and be costly. Natural excipients have drawn a lot of interest lately because of their affordability, biocompatibility, and biodegradability². A natural polymer made from *Tamarindus indica* seeds is called tamarind seed kernel powder (TSKP). Because TSKP exhibits outstanding disintegrant, swelling, and mucoadhesive qualities, it has been investigated as a possible excipient in medicinal formulations. The purpose of this study is to create and test atenolol tablets with TSKP as a natural disintegrant, examining its potential to improve tablet disintegration rate while providing a more

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patient-friendly and cost-effective alternative to synthetic disintegrants.

Figure 1. Structure of Tamarind Seed Polysaccharide.

Figure 2. Tamarind Seed.

Figure 3. Tamarind Kernel Powder.

2. Disintegration Property of Tamarind Kernel Powder^{1,2}:

TKP's disintegration mechanism consists of several essential factors:

Figure 4. Disintegration Property of Tamarind Kernel Powder.

3. Identification Test for Tamarind Kernel Powder³:

- The Result of **Molisch test of Carbohydrate is Positive** and **Ruthenium red test of Mucilage is also Positive.**

- Other tests such as Monosaccharide, Protein, Alkaloids, Tannins, Amino acid, Glycoside is Negative

4. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

MATERIALS:

Figure 5. Materials.

a) Used For Preparation of Fast Disintegrating Tablet:

1. Direct Compression³:

Figure 6. Method Used for Preparation of Fast Disintegrating Tablet (Direct Compression).

1. Methods Used to Prepare Rapid Disintegrating Tablets³:

Table 1. Methods Used to Prepare Rapid Disintegrating Tablet.

Direct Compression Method.	Wet Granulation Method.	Melt Granulation Method.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • combines active substances, excipients, and superdisintegrants. • Compress the mixture into tablets with a rotary press. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Combines active components, binder, and excipients • Granulate mixture with solvent (e.g. water, ethanol). • Drying and sifting the grains. • Granules are compressed into tablets. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Combine active components, excipients, and melt binder. • Heat the mixture to produce granules. • Cooling and sifting the grains. • Granules are compressed into tablets.

5. Formulation Table:

Table 2. Formulation Table

Sr. No	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
1	Atenolol	100	100	100	100	100	100
2	TKP	5	7.5	10	15	20	30
3	MCC	200	200	195	190	190	180

4	Lactose	77	72.5	75	75	70	70
5	Mg. Stearate	8	10	10	10	10	10
6	Talc	5	5	5	5	5	5
7	Avg. Wt.	395	395	395	395	395	395

6. Pharmacological Properties of Atenolol Drug⁴:

- Type: Beta-blocker (selective blocker of β 1-adrenergic receptor)
- Mechanism of Action: By preventing adrenaline from acting on the heart's β 1-adrenergic receptors, atenolol lowers heart rate.
- Pharmacokinetics:

1) Well, absorbed when taken orally (50–60%)

2) Distribution: widely dispersed, with the kidneys, liver, and heart having the highest quantities. 3) There is very little hepatic metabolism.

4) Elimination: Mostly eliminated unaltered in urine (85–100%)

7. Pre-Compression Studies of Tamarind Kernel Powder:

Table 3. Pre-Compression Studies of Tamarind Kernel Powder.

1) Bulk Density:	<p>Pouring the powder blend into a cylinder and recording its initial weight allows for calculation. Bulk volume is the starting volume. The following formula was used to determine the volume of the powder blend.</p> <p>Formula: Bulk Density: $\frac{\text{Mass of powder}}{\text{Volume of powder}}$</p>
2) Tapped Density:	<p>It can be defined as the ratio of a powder's tapped volume to its overall mass. The powder blend was poured into the measuring cylinder to ascertain it. On the harder surface, the cylinder was gently tapped 500 times, and the volume of powder that was tapped was recorded. The tapped volume was recorded after 1000 repetitions of tapping when there was a difference of more than 2% between two volumes. In a bulk density apparatus, tapping was carried out repeatedly until the ensuing volume differences were less than 2%. It was computed using the formula and expressed in g/ml⁵.</p> <p>Formula: Tapped density: $\frac{\text{Mass of powder}}{\text{Tapped volume of powder}}$</p>
3) Angle of Repose:	<p>To get the angle of repose, we applied the funnel approach. The mixture was run through a funnel that could be adjusted vertically until the cone's height (h) was attained. The Angle of Repose (θ) was calculated using the formula after the heap's radius (r) was measured⁶.</p> <p>Formula: Angle of Repose: $\tan \theta = \frac{h}{r}$</p>
4) Hausner's Ratio:	<p>HR serves as a proxy for powder flow ease. It is computed using the formula that follows⁷:</p> <p>Formula: Hausner's Ratio: $\frac{\text{Tapped density}}{\text{Bulk density}}$</p>
5) Carr's Index:	<p>It proves that the flow of a powder is what makes it compressible. The following is the Carr's index formula¹¹:</p>

	Formula: Carr's index: $\frac{D_t - D_b}{D_t} \times 100$
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8. Post-Compression Studies of Tamarind Kernel

Powder:

Table 4. Post-Compression Studies of Tamarind Kernel Powder.

1) Tablet Hardness:	In a test device that applies tension or bending stress, the force needed to shatter a tablet is called "tablet hardness." The effectiveness and overall performance of a tablet are greatly influenced by its hardness, especially in relation for patients use, packaging, and shipping ¹² .																				
2) Tablet Thickness:	Tablets were measured for thickness with a Vernier caliper.																				
3) Weight Variation:	<p>A test for weight variation was conducted to make sure a tablet had the right amount of medication. Analytical balances were used to determine the weight of each tablet. That was used to calculate the average weight. Next, each tablet's weight was compared to the average weight⁸.</p> <p>Weight of 10 tablets (mg)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Table 5. Weight of Tablets</p> <table border="1" style="margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto;"> <tr> <td>1.</td> <td>380</td> <td>6.</td> <td>395</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2.</td> <td>392</td> <td>7.</td> <td>385</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3.</td> <td>377</td> <td>8.</td> <td>392</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4.</td> <td>387</td> <td>9.</td> <td>389</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5.</td> <td>388</td> <td>10.</td> <td>380</td> </tr> </table> <p>10 tablets average weight is 386.5 mg.</p> <p>Weight variation restriction for tablets weighing <500 mg in accordance with different regulatory recommendations and pharmacopoeias:</p> <p>USP (United States Pharmacopoeia):</p> <p>For tablets < 250 mg: ±10%</p> <p>For tablets 250-500 mg: ±5%</p> <p>Calculation :</p> <p>Average weight of 1 tablet = 395 mg</p> <p>$395 \times 5 / 100 = 19.75$ mg</p> <p>$395 \pm 19.75 = 414.75$ or 375.25</p>	1.	380	6.	395	2.	392	7.	385	3.	377	8.	392	4.	387	9.	389	5.	388	10.	380
1.	380	6.	395																		
2.	392	7.	385																		
3.	377	8.	392																		
4.	387	9.	389																		
5.	388	10.	380																		
4) Friability:	<p>A sample of ten to twenty tablets was tested for friability using a USP-type Roche friabilator.</p> <p>Apparatus: A cylindrical drum (285 mm diameter, 190 mm depth) with a translucent plastic cover and a removable tray.</p> <p>Formula:</p> $\frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$ <p>Calculation:</p> $\frac{3865 - 3835}{3865} \times 100 = 0.7$																				
5) In Vitro Disintegration:	The tablet disintegrating test device was used to determine the tablet's disintegration time. Each tube of the tablet disintegration testing device contained six tablets. The media was kept at $37 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, and the amount of time needed for																				

	<p>the complete pill to dissolve was recorded. The duration required for a tablet or capsule to disintegrate in a controlled laboratory setting that mimics physiological fluids is known as the "in vitro disintegration time."</p> <p>Test Method: Apparatus: A USP Disintegration Apparatus or the disintegration tester with baskets¹³. Medium: Distilled Water Procedure: Put four tablets in baskets, then immerse them in a medium that is maintained at 37°C and watch.</p>
6)In Vitro Dissolution:	<p>A technique used in laboratories to mimic how a pharmaceutical product might dissolve in the human body is called in vitro dissolution testing. The test assesses the active pharmaceutical ingredient's (API) rate and degree of dissolution from the dosage form⁹.</p> <p>The contents of the dissolution medium are as follows: [900 milliliter Phosphate Buffer: Ph 6.8]</p> <p>Test:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Place the sample: Fill each basket with one dose unit. • Turn on the device: Start the timer and agitation. (RPM of 50) • Gather samples: At specified time intervals, remove samples. (5, 10, 15, 30, 45, 60 min.) • Examine samples: Utilize UV spectrophotometry to determine the concentration of dissolved drugs. • Record data: Record the dissolution profile (drug release percentage vs time) • Formula: Amount of drug release(mg/ml): $\frac{\text{Concentration} \times \text{Dissolution volume} \times \text{Dilution factor}}{1000}$ Percent Drug release: $\frac{\text{Amount of drug release} \times 1000}{\text{Total amount of drug in formulation (mg)}}$
7)UV Absorbance:	<p>The concept an active pharmaceutical ingredient (API)-containing solution's ability to absorb ultraviolet (UV) light is measured by the UV Absorbance test. The API's concentration and absorbance are intimately correlated.</p> <p>Measurement Steps for UV Absorbance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepare sample solution • Set the wavelength between 200 and 400 nm, or 277 nm. • Determine the blank's (distilled water) absorbance. • Determine sample absorbance. • Determine the absorbance difference¹⁰.

9.UV Absorbance And % Drug Release for Trial Batches. (F1,F2,F3,F4):

Table 6. UV Absorbance and % Drug Release for Trial Batches. (F1,F2,F3,F4)

Sr no.	Time (min)	Absorbance				Concentration (ug/ml)				% Drug Release			
		F1	F2	F3	F4	F1	F2	F3	F4	F1	F2	F3	F4

1.	5	0.014	0.015	0.020	0.029	0.24	0.29	0.54	0.99	2.20	2.85	4.48	6.95
2.	10	0.029	0.32	0.038	0.046	0.99	1.14	1.44	1.845	4.95	8.30	9.05	11.60
3.	15	0.052	0.57	0.065	0.076	2.14	2.39	2.79	3.34	9.30	14.55	18.11	24.06
4.	30	0.081	0.86	0.097	0.13	3.59	3.84	4.09	6.04	13.35	22.75	29.85	39.40
5.	45	0.10	0.10	0.12	0.15	4.54	4.54	5.54	7.04	19.90	30.90	45.90	56.40
6.	60	0.11	0.13	0.15	0.20	5.045	6.04	7.04	9.54	28.40	39.40	53.40	68.90

10.Observation Table: F5 UV Absorbance and Percent Drug Release:

Table 7.F5 Batch UV Absorbance and Percent Drug Release.

Sr. No	Time (min)	Absorbance	Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% Drug Release
1	5	0.035	1.295	7.15
2	10	0.057	2.39	21.55
3	15	0.083	3.69	33.25
4	30	0.15	7.045	63.40
5	45	0.190	9.04	71.40
6	60	0.23	11.04	82.40

Observation Table: F6 Batch (UV Absorbance):

Table 8.F6 Batch UV Absorbance and Percent Drug Release.

Sr. No	Time (min)	Absorbance	Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Wavelength (nm)
1	5	0.05	2.045	226
2	10	0.08	3.545	226
3	15	0.11	5.045	226
4	30	0.18	8.54	226
5	45	0.22	10.54	226
6	60	0.27	13.045	226

Figure 8. Calibration Curve of Atenolol (F6)

Figure 9. Time vs Drug Release.

11. Comparative Study of Time Vs Percent Drug Release of All Batches (F1, F2, F3, F4, F5, F6):

Figure 10. Comparative Study of Time vs % Drug Release of All Batches.(F1,F2,F3,F4,F5,F6)

12.RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

1)Pre-Compression Evaluation:

Table 9. Pre-compression Parameters

Sr. No	Test	Standard Value	Observed Value	Conclusion
✓	Bulk Density	0.40 – 0.60 g/ml	0.38 g/ml	Very loose
✓	Tapped Density	0.58 – 0.78 g/ml	0.60 g/ml	Very loose
✓	Angle of Repose	30 ⁰ – 45 ⁰	38 ⁰	Moderate Flow
✓	Carr’s Index	21 – 27 %	20 %	Fair
✓	Hausner Ratio	1.2 – 1.5	1.29	Passable

2)Post-Compression Evaluation:

Table 10. Post-compression Parameters

Sr. No	Parameter	Standard Value	Observed Value	Conclusion
➤	Hardness	4 – 12 kg/cm 2	4.1 kg/cm 2	Low
➤	Thickness	5 – 10 mm	10 mm	Pass
➤	Friability	0.5 – 1 %	0.7 %	Excellent
➤	Weight Variation	>500 mg ± 5%	414.75 or 375.25	Acceptable
➤	Disintegration	<15 min	9 min 52 sec	Good
➤	% Drug Release T90	30 – 60 min	42.67 min	Good

13.CONCLUSION:

According to the natural tamarind kernel powder's pre-compression and post-compression evaluation parameters listed above, our optimized F6 batch passes each of them, and the results were determined to be satisfactory within the given bounds, demonstrating good disintegrating property.

REFERENCES

1. Patel, J., & Patel, R. (2019). Development and evaluation of atenolol tablets using natural disintegrants. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 10(5), 1230-1236.
2. Sharma, P., & Sharma, V. (2018). Natural disintegrants in tablet formulation: A review. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Scientific Innovation*, 7(2), 141-146.
3. *Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms: Tablets Volume 1. Second Edition, Revised and Expanded* Edited by Herbert A. Lieberman, Leon Lachman, and Joseph B. Schwartz, 198-220
4. Amery, A.; liet, L.; Joosens, J.V.; Meekers, J.; Reybrouck, T. and Van Mieghem, W.: Preliminary report on the hemodynamic response of hypertensive patients treated with a beta-blocker (I.C.I. 66,082). *Acta Clinica Belgica* 28: 359 (1973).
5. Rowe RC, Paul JS, Sian CO. *Handbook of Pharmaceutical Excipients*. 6th ed. Washington, DC: Pharmaceutical Press; 2009. p. 45, 404, 424
6. U S A Pharmacopeial Convention. *National Formulary 35*. United States Pharmacopeia 40. Rockville: United States Pharmacopeial Committee; 2017. p. 2886-8.
7. Aulton ME, *Aulton's Pharmaceutics the Design and Manufacture of Medicines*. Philadelphia: Churchill Livingstone; 2013. p. 187-99
8. Preethi GB, Banerjee S, Shivakumar HN, Kumar MR. Formulation of fast-dissolving tablets of doxazosin mesylate drug by direct compression method. *Int J Appl Pharm* 2017;9:22-8. doi: 10.22159/ijap.2017v9i5.18168
9. Jadhav D, Kharat R, Jhadav S, Patil MK. Design and evaluation of sustained release matrix tablet of propranolol hydrochloride. *Indo Am J Pharm Res*. 2015:1109-17.
10. G Verma, DR. M Mishra, "Development and Optimization of UV VIS Spectroscopy-A Review", *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2018,7(11),1170-1180
11. Mohapatra S, Pattanaik P, Sudam C. Role of super disintegrants for in-vitro characterization of loratadine Oro dispersible tablets. *Int J Pharm Sci* 2012;4:319-23.
12. Khar Roop K et al. "Lachman & Lieberman; The Theory and Practice of industrial Pharmacy" IVth Published by CBS publisher & distributor, 2015;449-545
13. B. M Mithal, *A Text book of Pharmaceutical Formulation*, Vallabh Prakashan, New Delhi, India, 1997; 114-165.

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